

Studies in Spiroheterocycles. Part-XVIII. Synthesis and Antifertility Activity of New Fluorine containing 4',5'-Cycloalkyl-2'-phenyl-spiro[3*H*-indole-3,3'-[3*H*]pyrazol]-2(1*H*)-ones

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A series of new fluorine containing 4',5'-cycloalkyl-2'-phenyl-spiro[3*H*-indole-3,3'-[3*H*]pyrazol]-2(1*H*)-ones and their *N*-substituted derivatives have been synthesised and characterised by their elemental analyses, ir, pmr and mass spectral studies. Representative compounds have been screened for their anti-implantation activity.

VARIOUS indole¹, pyrazole² and indazole^{3,4,5} derivatives have been investigated as antifertility agents and found useful as contraceptives. 1-(2,4-Dichlorobenzyl)-1*H*-indazole-3-carboxylic acid directly affects the rat testes and is effective as a partially reversible antifertility agent⁶. Further, 3-aminohexahydroindazole is useful as a contraceptive⁶ and the introduction of *N,N*-dialkylaminoalkyl group is reported to increase the activity⁷.

These observations led us to synthesise fluorine containing 4',5'-cycloalkyl-2'-phenyl-spiro[3*H*-indole-3,3'-[3*H*]pyrazol]-2(1*H*)-ones and their derivatives by incorporation of indole and pyrazole nuclei through a spiro-carbon atom and these compounds may act as possible antifertility agents. Although the reaction of 3-arylmethyleneindol-2-ones with hydrazine hydrate and phenylhydrazine have been investigated earlier⁸⁻¹¹, but the reaction of 3-(2-oxocyclopentylidene/hexylidene)indol-2-ones with phenylhydrazine is not reported in the literature and has been carried out for the first time. Besides, these compounds incorporate fluorine in the critical 5- and 6-positions of indole ring involved in enzymatic hydroxylation and conjugation and may, therefore, impart significant changes in biological activities¹².

3-Hydroxy-3-(2-oxocyclopentyl/hexyl)indol-2-ones (1a-d) were obtained by the reaction of various substituted-indole-2,3-diones with a cyclic ketone (cyclopentanone/cyclohexanone) and on dehydration with HCl-CH₃COOH, gave 3-(2-oxocyclopentylidene/hexylidene)indol-2-ones (2a-d)¹³. Reaction of 2a-d with phenyl/fluorophenylhydrazine resulted in cyclisation, affording 4',5'-cyclopentyl/hexyl-2'-phenyl/fluorophenyl-spiro[3*H*-indole-3,3'-[3*H*]pyrazol]-2(1*H*)-ones (3a-f). Different *N*-substituted derivatives (4a-c) were also prepared by Mannich reaction of 3b, 3e and 3f (Scheme 1).

- 1a, 2a'; X=H, n=1
1b, 2b; X=H, n=2
1c, 2c; X=5-F, n=1
1d, 2d; X=6-F, n=2
3a-f; X=H, Y=C₆F₅, n=1
3b; X=H, Y=C₆F₅, n=2
3c; X=H, Y=4-F₂C₆H₄, n=2
3d; X=5-F, Y=C₆H₅, n=1
3e; X=5-F, Y=C₆F₅, n=1
3f; X=6-F, Y=C₆F₅, n=2

- 4a; X=H, Y=C₆F₅, n=2, R¹=
4b; X=5-F, Y=C₆F₅, n=1, R¹=
4c; X=6-F, Y=C₆F₅, n=2, R¹=

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) (ii) HCl-CH₃COOH, (iii) H₂NNHY, (iv) HCHO, HNR₂

Results and Discussion

Spectral studies : Ir spectra of compounds (1a-d) show signals at 3 350-3 000 (br, NH, OH), 2 900-2 850 (CH₂), 1 670 and 1 610 cm⁻¹ (two, C=O). Disappearance of OH signal in compounds 2a-d indicates the formation of these compounds. In the pmr spectra of 3a-f, characteristic signals are obtained at δ 1.2 (t, CH₃), 1.9 (q, CH₂), 2.2-2.7 (m, CH₂CH₂ or CH₂), 3.5 (dd, CH), 6.7-7.8 (m, ArH) and 8.9-6.0 (s, NH). In pmr spectra of 4a-c, NH signal of 3b, 3e, and 3f disappears and additional resonance signals are observed at δ 1.0-4.5 ppm due to CH₂N(CH₂)₂ and CH₂OCH₂ or CH₂CH₂CH₂. Mass spectral studies further support their formation as molecular ion peaks (M⁺) at m/z 245 (1b), 227 (2b), 407 (3b) and 506 (4a) correspond to their molecular weights.

Antifertility activity : Representative compounds 3e, 3f, 4a and 4b were screened for their anti-implantation activity in adult female rats of Sprague Dawley strain. The compounds were suspended in distilled water with the help of gum acacia and administered orally at 20 mg/kg P.C. once daily for 7 days. The rats were killed on the day 10 P.C. and the number of implantation sites were recorded (Table 1). None of the compounds was found to be active.

TABLE 1—POST-COITAL, ANTIFERTILITY EFFICACY

Compd. no.	Dose ^a mg/kg	Total rats	Pregnant ^b rats	Implantations ^b (mean ± SE, range)
3e	20.0	4	3	12.67 ± 0.67 (12-14)
3f	20.0	4	3	11.33 ± 2.33 (9-16)
4a	20.0	4	4	13.50 ± 2.69 (6-18)
4b	20.0	4	4	10.00 ± 0.71 (8-11)

^aDays 1-5 post-coitum, oral. ^bDay 10 post-coitum.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF 3-HYDROXY-3-(2-OXOCYCLOALKYL)INDOL-2-ONES (1a-d)

Compd. no.	X	n	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
						O	H	N
1a	H	1	226	75	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ NO ₂	67.51	5.41	6.00
						(67.53)	(5.62)	(6.06)
1b	H	2	216	70	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ NO ₂	68.51	6.11	5.68
						(68.57)	(6.12)	(5.71)
1c	5-F	1	250d	80	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ FNO ₂	62.58	4.80	5.56
						(62.65)	(4.81)	(5.62)
1d	6-F	2	192	80	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ FNO ₂	63.71	5.29	5.31
						(63.87)	(5.32)	(5.32)

TABLE 3—PHYSICAL DATA OF 3-(2-OXOCYCLOALKYLIDENE)INDOL-2-ONES (2a-c)

Compd. no.	X	n	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
						O	H	N
2a	H	1	260	65	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ NO ₂	73.13	5.12	6.52
						(73.23)	(5.16)	(6.57)
2b	H	2	240	65	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₂	74.00	5.68	6.08
						(74.00)	(5.72)	(6.16)
2c	5-F	1	157	60	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ FNO ₂	67.52	4.32	6.00
						(67.53)	(4.32)	(6.06)
2d	6-F	2	160	60	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ FNO ₂	68.54	4.85	5.69
						(68.57)	(4.89)	(5.71)

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Perkin-Elmer RB 12 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a Brucker-30 and 50 spectrometers. Purity was routinely checked by tlc.

3-Hydroxy-3-(2-oxocyclohexyl/pentyl)indol-2-one (1) : A mixture of indole-2,3-dione (0.01 mol), cyclohexanone/cyclopentanone (1.1 ml), diethylamine (0.3 ml) and ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 1 h. On cooling, the resulting crystals were filtered, washed well with ethanol, dried in air and recrystallised from ethanol. A similar method was used for the preparation of other members (Table 2).

1,3-Dihydro-3-(2-oxocyclohexylidene/pentylidene)-indol-2-one (2) : 3-Hydroxy-3-(2-oxocyclohexyl/pentyl)indol-2-one (0.01 mol) was dissolved in hot acetic acid (4 ml) and treated with concentrated HCl (0.5 ml). The solution was then boiled for 2 min and poured into ice-cold water to give the title compound. The crude product was filtered, washed well with water and dried in air. Other members of the series were prepared similarly (Table 3).

4',5'-Cyclohexyl/pentyl-2'-phenyl/fluorophenyl-spiro [3H-indole-3,3'-(3H)-pyrazol]-2(1H)-one (3) : A mixture of 1,3-dihydro-3-(2-oxocyclohexylidene/pentylidene)-indol-2-one (0.01 mol), phenyl/fluorophenylhydrazine (0.012 mol) and ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 4.5 h. On cooling, the resulting crystals were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. A similar method was used for the preparation of other analogs (Table 4).

TABLE 4—PHYSICAL DATA OF 4',5'-CYCLOALKYL-2'-PHENYL/PFLUOROPHENYL-SPIRO[3H-INDOLE-3,3'-[3H]PYRAZOL]-2(1H)-ONES (3a-f)

Compd. no.	X	Y	n	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
							C	H	N
3a	H	C ₆ F ₅	1	130	60	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ F ₅ N ₂ O	58.00 (58.01)	3.02 (3.05)	10.62 (10.68)
3b	H	C ₆ F ₅	2	>300	55	C ₃₀ H ₁₄ F ₅ N ₂ O	58.92 (58.96)	3.41 (3.48)	10.30 (10.31)
3c	H	4-FC ₆ H ₄	2	245	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ FN ₂ O	71.64 (71.64)	5.35 (5.37)	12.51 (12.53)
3d	5-F	C ₆ H ₅	1	229	45	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ FN ₂ O	71.00 (71.02)	4.98 (4.98)	13.06 (13.08)
3e	5-F	C ₆ F ₅	1	198	60	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ F ₅ N ₂ O	55.45 (55.47)	2.63 (2.67)	10.19 (10.21)
3f	6-F	C ₆ F ₅	2	203	60	C ₃₀ H ₁₄ F ₅ N ₂ O	56.46 (56.47)	3.04 (3.05)	9.86 (9.88)

TABLE 5—PHYSICAL DATA OF 1-DIALKYLAMINOMETHYL-4',5'-CYCLOALKYL-2'-PENTAFLUOROPHENYL-SPIRO[3H-INDOLE-3,3'-[3H]PYRAZOL]-2-ONES (4a-c)

Compd. no.	X	Y	R ¹	n	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
								C	H	N
4a	H	C ₆ F ₅		2	135	80	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ F ₅ N ₄ O ₂	59.23 (59.28)	4.51 (4.54)	11.00 (11.06)
4b	5-F	C ₆ F ₅		1	135	75	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ F ₆ N ₄ O	59.00 (59.05)	4.30 (4.33)	11.00 (11.02)
4c	6-F	C ₆ F ₅		2	175	80	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ F ₆ N ₄ O ₂	57.21 (57.25)	4.13 (4.19)	10.65 (10.68)

4',5'-Cyclohexyl|pentyl-2'-pentafluorophenyl-1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl-spiro[3H-indole-3,3'-[3H]pyrazol]-2-one (4): A mixture of 4',5'-cyclohexyl/pentyl-2'-pentafluorophenyl-spiro[3H-indole-3,3'-[3H]pyrazol]-2(1H)-one (0.01 mol), formaldehyde (40% ; 0.15 mol), morpholine/piperidine (0.0012 mol) and ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 45 min. On cooling, the resulting crystals were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 5).

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